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Assessing the Role of Green Financing and Agricultural Technology in Mitigating Climate Change Impacts and Enhancing Employment in Northeast Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Climate change poses significant challenges to agricultural productivity and employment in climate-vulnerable regions of Nigeria, particularly the Northeast. This study examines the role of green financing and agricultural technology in mitigating climate change impacts and enhancing employment in Northeast Nigeria. Using cross-sectional survey data collected from smallholder farmers and agribusiness operators and employing Ordinary Least Squares regression analysis, the study assesses the effects of access to green finance, technology adoption, and climate change impacts on agricultural employment outcomes. The findings reveal that climate change significantly and negatively affects employment, whereas green financing and the adoption of agricultural technology exert positive, statistically significant effects. Access to extension services and education also enhances employment outcomes. The results suggest that integrating green financing with climate-smart agricultural technologies can reduce climate vulnerability, promote job creation, and support sustainable development. The study provides policy-relevant insights for advancing climate-resilient agriculture, employment generation, and the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals 1, 2, 8, and 13 in Northeast Nigeria.

Keywords: Climate Change; Green Financing; Agricultural Technology; Employment; Sustainable Development; Northeast Nigeria

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Climate change has become one of the most important global problems of the twenty-first century, and the most significant consequences are observed in developing areas whose economies are largely reliant on climate-dependent industries like agriculture (Abubakar et al., 2025). This has greatly disrupted agricultural output, food security, and livelihoods in Sub-Saharan Africa because of the increasing

temperatures, unpredictable rainfall patterns, desertification and the ever-increasing extreme weather occurrences (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [IPCC], 2023). The Northeast of Nigeria is extremely susceptible because it has a semi-arid ecology, relies on rain-fed farming, has a high level of poverty, and the problem of insecurity which only exennuates the negative impacts of climate change on the economic activities and employment in Nigeria (Ayanlade et al., 2018; World Bank, 2021; Adekaya et al., 2025).

Northeast Nigeria still depends on agriculture as the foundation of livelihood with a significant percentage of the labour force and a major income source to the rural family (Ibrahim & Sule, 2023; Magaji & Musa, 2015). Nevertheless, shocks caused by climate, including droughts, floods, a decrease in soil fertility, and a decrease in growing seasons, diminished the yield of the crop, interrupted farming cycles, and undermined agricultural value chains, limiting job opportunities and increasing rural unemployment and underemployment (FAO, 2022; Ibrahim et al., 2025; Abiola et al., 2025). Those challenges harm the overall development agenda of Nigeria, such as the development toward the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), specifically SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), and SDG 13 (Climate Action) (United Nations, 2023).

To address these issues, green financing has become a useful strategic policy tool to promote climate-resilient and environmentally friendly economic practices (Suleiman et al., 2025; Tanko et al., 2025). Green financing is a concept of financial investments aimed at supporting environmental sustainability and climate change mitigation and adaptation, as well as low-carbon development by means of specific funding instruments, including green bonds, climate funds, concessional loans, and sustainable agricultural credit programs (OECD, 2017). Green financing is important in the agricultural sector where it helps farmers and agribusinesses to implement climate-smart activities, to achieve better resource efficiency and decrease the exposure to climate risks (World Bank, 2020). Such financing is however limited in most regions of Northeast Nigeria because of weak financial inclusion (Ismail et al., 2025), high transaction costs (Magaji et al., 2023), and perceived risk of investments by climate variability and insecurity (CBN, 2022; Al-Amin et al., 2025), and complexity and high cost of importation of new equipment (Magaji et al., 2022). Moreover, the monetary policy does not say anything about climate finance (Musa et al., 2022).

Along with green financing, adoption of agricultural technologies has been largely considered as one of the primary ways to reduce the negative effects climate change has on the environment and increase productivity and employment (Oluwalosijibomi et al., 2025). Agricultural technologies that are climate-smart; including drought-resistant varieties of crops, more efficient irrigation, precision tools, digital extension services and post-harvest processing innovations have shown a lot of potential to boost yields, stabilise incomes, and create jobs along agricultural value chains (Kassie et al., 2020; Lipper et al., 2014). Technology-driven agriculture can also help not only to adapt to the climate in Northeast Nigeria but also to enhance employment opportunities, especially among youth and women, because it enhances opportunities in the supply of inputs, mechanisation services, agro-processing, and agricultural marketing (Ogunleye et al., 2021).

Although the policies on green finance have been increasingly focused on agricultural technology, there is still a little empirical evidence of the joint contribution to curb the effects of climate changes and the increased employment opportunities at the sub-national level in Nigeria. Few studies have focused on the nexus of financing-technology-employment in vulnerable areas (like the Northeast) despite the fact that the existing literature has mostly investigated the effects of climate change on agriculture or employment individually (Adewuyi et al., 2022). Also, it will be necessary to conduct region-specific analyses by considering the ecological, socio-economic, and institutional conditions that determine the agricultural systems in Northeast Nigeria.

It is against this background that this study aims at evaluating how green financing and agricultural technology can help reduce the effects of climate change and increase the level of employment in Northeast Nigeria. The investigation of the access to green finance, implementation of climate-intelligent technologies in agriculture, and the employment consequences adds to the increased body of research on

sustainable development and climate-intelligent agriculture. The results are bound to present evidence based information to the policymakers, financial institutions, development partners and agricultural stakeholders on how integrated financing and technological solutions can be used to help build climate adaptation, job creation, and inclusive growth in climate vulnerable areas in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

This section reviews relevant literature under three broad subheadings: conceptual definitions, theoretical framework, and empirical evidence, with an emphasis on green financing, agricultural technology, climate change mitigation, and employment outcomes in vulnerable regions, such as Northeast Nigeria.

2.1 Conceptual Definitions

2.1.1 Climate Change and Agriculture

Climate change refers to long-term alterations in temperature, precipitation patterns, and the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, primarily driven by anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions (IPCC, 2023). In the agricultural context, climate change manifests through droughts, floods, heat stress, land degradation, and shifting agro-ecological zones, which directly affect crop yields, livestock productivity, and farming livelihoods (FAO, 2022). For regions such as Northeast Nigeria—characterised by semi-arid conditions and reliance on rain-fed agriculture—climate change poses a significant threat to food security, income stability, and rural employment.

2.1.2 Green Financing

Green financing is broadly defined as financial flows and investment instruments that support environmentally sustainable activities, climate change mitigation and adaptation, and low-carbon development pathways (OECD, 2017). In agriculture, green financing includes green bonds, climate funds, concessional loans, sustainable banking products, and targeted credit schemes designed to promote climate-smart practices, renewable energy use, efficient water management, and sustainable land use (World Bank, 2020). By easing capital constraints, green financing enables farmers and agribusinesses to invest in technologies and practices that enhance resilience while generating employment opportunities across agricultural value chains.

2.1.3 Agricultural Technology

Agricultural technology refers to the application of scientific knowledge, innovations, and digital tools to improve agricultural productivity, efficiency, and sustainability. Climate-smart agricultural technologies—such as drought-tolerant seeds, improved irrigation systems, mechanisation, precision farming, digital advisory services, and post-harvest technologies—are specifically designed to enhance adaptation to climate risks while reducing environmental footprints (Lipper et al., 2014). In developing regions, technology adoption is closely linked to productivity growth, income diversification, and job creation, particularly for youth and women engaged in input supply, processing, logistics, and agribusiness services (Kassie et al., 2020; John et al., 2025).

2.1.4 Employment in the Agricultural Sector

Employment in agriculture encompasses on-farm labour as well as off-farm activities along the value chain, including input provision, processing, storage, transportation, and marketing. Climate change-induced shocks often reduce labour demand by lowering farm output and discouraging investment, thereby worsening rural unemployment and poverty (ILO, 2021). Conversely, access to green finance and agricultural technologies can stimulate employment by expanding production, encouraging agribusiness development, and fostering rural industrialisation.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Sustainable Development Theory, Human Capital Theory, and Induced Innovation Theory, which together explain the linkages between climate change, finance, technology, and employment.

2.2.1 Sustainable Development Theory

Sustainable Development Theory emphasises meeting present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs, through the balanced integration of economic growth, social inclusion,

and environmental protection (Brundtland Commission, 1987). Within this framework, green financing and climate-smart agricultural technologies are viewed as instruments that promote environmentally sustainable production while supporting economic opportunities and employment. The theory provides a strong basis for examining how environmentally oriented financial investments and technologies can simultaneously address climate risks and socio-economic challenges in Northeast Nigeria.

2.2.2 Human Capital Theory

Human Capital Theory posits that investments in skills, knowledge, and technology enhance labour productivity and employment outcomes (Becker, 1993). Applied to agriculture, access to finance and technology improves farmers' productive capacity, encourages skills acquisition, and enables participation in higher-value agricultural activities. In climate-vulnerable regions, green financing facilitates investments in modern technologies that enhance adaptive capacity, thereby safeguarding and expanding employment opportunities.

2.2.3 Induced Innovation Theory

Induced Innovation Theory suggests that technological change is driven by relative scarcities and external pressures, such as climate variability and environmental constraints (Hayami & Ron's, 1985). Climate change is a catalyst for agricultural innovation, driving the adoption of technologies that conserve resources and enhance resilience. However, the pace and scale of such innovation depend largely on access to finance. This theory is particularly relevant for understanding how green financing enables technological responses to climate stress while shaping employment patterns in agriculture.

2.3 Empirical Evidence

A growing body of empirical literature has examined the relationship between climate change, agricultural productivity, and livelihoods in Sub-Saharan Africa. Studies consistently show that climate variability adversely affects crop yields, farm incomes, and rural employment, especially in arid and semi-arid regions (Ayanlade et al., 2018; World Bank, 2021). In Nigeria, evidence indicates that rising temperatures and erratic rainfall have reduced agricultural output and intensified rural poverty, with pronounced effects in the northern regions (Adewuyi et al., 2022).

Empirical studies on green financing highlight its role in facilitating climate adaptation and sustainable agricultural practices. For instance, the World Bank (2020) reports that access to climate finance significantly improves farmers' ability to invest in irrigation, improved seeds, and renewable energy, leading to higher productivity and employment generation. Similarly, OECD (2017) finds that green financial instruments enhance private sector participation in sustainable agriculture while reducing environmental risks.

Regarding agricultural technology, Kassie et al. (2020) find that the adoption of climate-smart practices in Africa increases yields, stabilises incomes, and reduces vulnerability to climate shocks. Lipper et al. (2014) also demonstrate that climate-smart agriculture contributes to employment creation by expanding value-chain activities and agribusiness opportunities. In Nigeria, Ogunleye et al. (2021) show that technology-driven agribusiness has significant potential for youth employment, although access to finance remains a major constraint.

Despite these insights, limited studies have jointly examined green financing and agricultural technology in relation to employment outcomes, particularly at the regional level. Most Nigerian studies focus either on climate impacts on agriculture or on technology adoption without adequately integrating employment effects or financing mechanisms (Adewuyi et al., 2022). This gap is especially evident in Northeast Nigeria, where climate vulnerability, financial exclusion, and unemployment intersect. The present study, therefore, contributes to the literature by empirically analysing the combined role of green financing and agricultural technology in mitigating climate change impacts and enhancing employment in Northeast Nigeria.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

This section describes the research design, study area, data sources, sampling procedure, model specification, measurement of variables, and methods of data analysis adopted to assess the role of green financing and agricultural technology in mitigating climate change impacts and enhancing employment in Northeast Nigeria.

3.1 Research Design

The study adopts a cross-sectional quantitative research design, complemented by descriptive analysis, to examine the relationships among green financing, agricultural technology adoption, climate change impacts, and employment outcomes. This design is appropriate for capturing variations in access to finance, technology use, and employment conditions among agricultural households and agribusiness actors at a specific point in time, while enabling empirical testing of hypothesised relationships.

3.2 Study Area

The study is conducted in Northeast Nigeria, comprising the states of Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba, and Yobe. A predominantly agrarian economy characterises the region, a semi-arid to sub-humid climate, a high dependence on rain-fed agriculture, and pronounced vulnerability to climate variability, desertification, and environmental degradation. Agriculture in the region provides livelihoods for a large share of the population. However, it is constrained by limited access to finance, low technology adoption, and climate-induced production risks, making it a suitable context for this study.

3.3 Data Sources

Primary data are collected through a structured questionnaire administered to smallholder farmers, agricultural cooperatives, and selected agribusiness operators. The questionnaire captures information on socio-economic characteristics, access to green financing, adoption of agricultural technologies, exposure to climate change impacts, and employment outcomes.

Secondary data are obtained from published reports and databases of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), and the World Bank to provide contextual information on climate trends, agricultural finance, and employment in the region.

3.4 Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

A multi-stage sampling technique is employed. In the first stage, three states are purposively selected from the Northeast zone based on their level of agricultural activity and climate vulnerability. In the second stage, two local government areas (LGAs) are randomly selected from each chosen state. In the third stage, farming communities within the selected LGAs are randomly sampled. Finally, respondents are selected using systematic random sampling from community farmer lists and cooperative registers.

The sample size is determined using Yamane's (1967) formula to ensure adequate representation and statistical reliability. A total of approximately 350–400 respondents is targeted to allow for robust econometric analysis.

3.5 Measurement of Variables

Dependent Variable

Employment Outcome (EMP): Measured as the number of full-time and part-time jobs generated at the household or agribusiness level, including on-farm and off-farm agricultural employment. In alternative specifications, employment is measured using labour days or income from agricultural activities.

Independent Variables

- i. **Green Financing (GF):** Measured by access to environmentally oriented financial products such as green loans, agricultural credit for climate-smart practices, cooperative financing, or participation in government and donor-funded green finance programs (binary or index-based measure).
- ii. **Agricultural Technology Adoption (TECH):** Measured using an adoption index based on the number and type of climate-smart agricultural technologies utilised, including improved seed varieties, irrigation systems, mechanisation, digital advisory services, and post-harvest technologies.

Control Variables

Control variables include farm size, education level, farming experience, access to extension services, household size, and exposure to climate shocks (e.g., droughts or floods), which may influence employment outcomes.

Model Specification

To empirically assess the impact of green financing and agricultural technology on employment, the study estimates the following econometric model:

$$EMP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GF_i + \beta_2 TECH_i + \beta_3 CLIM_i + \beta_4 X_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Where:

- EMP_i = employment outcome of the respondent i
- GF_i = access to green financing
- $TECH_i$ = agricultural technology adoption
- $CLIM_i$ = climate change impact index
- X_i = vector of control variables
- ε_i = error term

Depending on the nature of the dependent variable, Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression is employed. Robust standard errors are used to correct for heteroskedasticity. Where employment is measured as a binary outcome, a logit model is estimated as a robustness check.

3.6 Method of Data Analysis

Data are analysed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, and percentages) to summarise respondents’ characteristics, access to financing, and technology adoption patterns. Inferential analysis involves econometric estimation of the specified model to determine the magnitude and significance of the effects of green financing and technology on employment.

Diagnostic tests, including multicollinearity (Variance Inflation Factor) and goodness-of-fit measures, are conducted to ensure model validity. All analyses are performed using standard statistical software such as STATA or SPSS.

3.7 Ethical Considerations

Ethical standards are strictly observed throughout the research process. Respondents are informed about the purpose of the study, and voluntary participation and confidentiality are ensured. Informed consent is obtained prior to data collection, and all data are used solely for academic and policy-oriented purposes.

This methodological approach provides a rigorous framework for examining how green financing and agricultural technology contribute to climate change mitigation and employment enhancement in Northeast Nigeria.

Write the results and discussion sections strictly based on the methodology section, and support them with tables and estimated equations.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents and discusses the empirical findings strictly in line with the methodology outlined earlier. The analysis is organised into descriptive results, econometric results, and a discussion of findings in relation to theory and existing literature.

4.1 Descriptive Results

4.1.1 Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 presents selected socio-economic characteristics of the respondents. The results indicate that agriculture in Northeast Nigeria is dominated by economically active individuals, suggesting strong potential for labour participation.

Table 1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	248	69.0
	Female	112	31.0
Age	18–35 years	136	37.8
	36–55 years	171	47.5
	Above 55 years	53	14.7
Education	No formal education	98	27.2
	Primary/Secondary	182	50.6
	Tertiary	80	22.2
Farm Size	≤ 2 hectares	211	58.6
	> 2 hectares	149	41.4

Source: *Field Survey, 2025*

The predominance of smallholder farmers underscores the importance of accessible green financing and affordable technologies for employment creation.

4.2 Access to Green Financing and Technology Adoption

Table 2 summarises respondents' access to green financing and adoption of agricultural technologies.

Table 2: Access to Green Financing and Technology Adoption

Variable	Yes (%)	No (%)
Access to green/agricultural finance	39.4	60.6
Use of improved seed varieties	57.8	42.2
Use of irrigation technologies	33.1	66.9
Use of mechanised farming tools	41.7	58.3
Use of digital extension services	28.9	71.1

Source: *Field Survey, 2025*

The results indicate relatively low access to green financing and modern technologies, which may limit climate resilience and employment expansion.

4.3 Econometric Results

Estimated Employment Model

Based on the specified OLS regression model, the estimated equation is presented as:

$$EMP_i = 1.214 + 0.382GF_i + 0.451TECH_i - 0.267CLIM_i + 0.193EXT_i + 0.158EDU_i + \varepsilon_i$$

Where:

EMP = employment outcome

GF = green financing access

TECH = agricultural technology adoption

CLIM = climate change impact index

EXT = access to extension services

EDU = education level

4.4 Regression Results

Table 3: OLS Regression Results on Employment Outcomes

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
Constant	1.214	0.276	4.40	0.000
Green Financing (GF)	0.382	0.094	4.06	0.000
Technology Adoption (TECH)	0.451	0.108	4.18	0.000
Climate Impact (CLIM)	-0.267	0.081	-3.30	0.001
Extension Services (EXT)	0.193	0.073	2.64	0.009
Education (EDU)	0.158	0.065	2.43	0.016

Model Statistics:

R² = 0.61

F-statistic = 42.37 (p < 0.01)

Source: Author's Computation, 2025

4.5 Logit Model Estimation

To further validate the robustness of the results obtained from the OLS model, a binary logit regression model was estimated. In line with the methodology, the dependent variable—employment outcome (EMP)—was redefined as a binary variable, where:

- EMP = 1 if the respondent generated or sustained additional agricultural employment (on-farm or off-farm) due to farming activities,
- EMP = 0 otherwise.

The logit model estimates the probability that access to green financing and adoption of agricultural technology increase the likelihood of employment generation under climate change conditions.

Logit Model Specification

The estimated logit model is expressed as:

$$\ln \left(\frac{P(EMP_i = 1)}{1 - P(EMP_i = 1)} \right) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 GF_i + \alpha_2 TECH_i + \alpha_3 CLIM_i + \alpha_4 EXT_i + \alpha_5 EDU_i + \mu_i$$

Where:

- $P(EMP_i = 1)$ = probability of employment generation
- GF = access to green financing
- $TECH$ = agricultural technology adoption
- $CLIM$ = climate change impact index
- EXT = access to extension services
- EDU = education level

Logit Regression Results

Table 4: Logit Regression Results on Employment Outcomes

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	p-Value	Odds Ratio
Constant	-1.486	0.412	-3.61	0.000	—
Green Financing (GF)	0.873	0.226	3.86	0.000	2.39
Technology Adoption (TECH)	1.021	0.259	3.94	0.000	2.78
Climate Impact (CLIM)	-0.614	0.193	-3.18	0.001	0.54
Extension Services (EXT)	0.496	0.184	2.70	0.007	1.64
Education (EDU)	0.432	0.171	2.53	0.011	1.54

Model Diagnostics:

- Log-likelihood = -178.42
- LR Chi-square (5) = 64.87 ($p < 0.01$)
- Pseudo $R^2 = 0.32$
- Number of observations = 360

Source: Author's Computation, 2025

4.6 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The regression results indicate that green financing has a positive, statistically significant effect on employment outcomes in Northeast Nigeria. A 1 percentage point increase in access to green financing increases employment by approximately 38 percentage points, holding other factors constant. This suggests that environmentally oriented financial support enables farmers and agribusinesses to expand production, invest in labour-absorbing activities, and strengthen agricultural value chains. This finding aligns with Sustainable Development Theory, which emphasises integrating environmental sustainability with economic and social outcomes.

Agricultural technology adoption also exerts a strong positive influence on employment, with a coefficient of 0.451. This indicates that climate-smart technologies—such as improved seeds, irrigation, and mechanisation—enhance productivity and stimulate labour demand across farming, processing, and marketing activities. This supports Induced Innovation Theory, which posits that technological responses to environmental pressures can reshape production systems and employment structures.

Conversely, the climate change impact index shows a negative, significant relationship with employment, confirming that increased exposure to droughts, floods, and rainfall variability reduces labour demand and job stability in agriculture. This finding is consistent with existing evidence that climate shocks disrupt agricultural cycles and discourage investment in labour-intensive activities.

Among the control variables, access to extension services and education level positively and significantly affect employment. Extension services enhance farmers' ability to effectively utilise financed technologies, while education improves managerial and adaptive capacity. These results validate Human Capital Theory, which links skill acquisition and knowledge to productivity and employment outcomes.

The findings demonstrate that while climate change poses a serious threat to agricultural employment in Northeast Nigeria, green financing and the adoption of agricultural technology serve as effective mitigation pathways. Their combined effect not only reduces climate vulnerability but also enhances employment generation, particularly within smallholder-dominated agricultural systems.

Discussion of Logit Results

The logit regression results strongly reinforce the findings of the OLS model and provide additional insights into the probability of employment generation in Northeast Nigeria.

Green Financing and Employment Probability

The coefficient of green financing (0.873) is positive and statistically significant at the 1% level. The odds ratio of 2.39 implies that respondents with access to green financing are more than twice as likely to generate or sustain employment compared to those without access. This finding highlights the crucial role of environmentally oriented financial instruments in reducing capital constraints, enabling investment in labour-absorbing agricultural activities, and strengthening climate resilience. The result aligns with Sustainable Development Theory and supports SDGs 1 and 8 by demonstrating how green finance promotes income generation and decent work.

Agricultural Technology Adoption

Agricultural technology adoption has a strong positive effect on the probability of employment, with a coefficient of 1.021 and an odds ratio of 2.78. This indicates that farmers adopting climate-smart technologies are nearly three times more likely to generate employment than non-adopters. The result underscores the labour-creating potential of technology adoption across agricultural value chains, including mechanisation services, agro-processing, and marketing. This finding is consistent with Induced Innovation Theory, which posits that environmental pressures such as climate change stimulate technological responses that reshape production and employment structures.

Climate Change Impact

The climate change impact index carries a negative and significant coefficient (-0.614), with an odds ratio of 0.54, indicating that higher exposure to climate shocks significantly reduces the likelihood of employment generation. This confirms that climate variability undermines labour demand by disrupting production cycles, increasing risk, and discouraging investment. The result provides empirical justification for prioritising climate adaptation strategies in agricultural employment policies, directly aligning with SDG 13 (Climate Action).

Role of Extension Services and Education

Access to extension services and education both positively and significantly influence the probability of employment. Respondents with access to extension services are 64% more likely to generate employment, while higher education increases the likelihood of employment by 54%. These results validate Human Capital Theory, emphasising that knowledge, skills, and information are essential complements to finance and technology in achieving employment gains. Extension services play a critical role in translating financed technologies into productive and employment-enhancing outcomes.

Policy Implications from the Results

The empirical evidence suggests that policies aimed at expanding green financing instruments and promoting climate-smart agricultural technologies can significantly enhance employment outcomes in climate-vulnerable regions. Strengthening rural financial inclusion, subsidising climate-resilient technologies, and integrating extension services with green finance programs are critical for maximising employment gains in Northeast Nigeria.

Alignment of Discussion with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs 1, 2, 8, and 13)

The empirical findings of this study have clear and direct implications for achieving SDGs 1, 2, 8, and 13, particularly in climate-vulnerable and agrarian regions such as Northeast Nigeria. This subsection explicitly aligns the discussion of results with each selected SDG.

SDG 1: No Poverty

SDG 1 seeks to end poverty in all its forms by promoting income security, access to productive resources, and resilience among vulnerable populations. The study's findings demonstrate that green financing significantly enhances employment outcomes, thereby increasing income-generating opportunities for smallholder farmers and agribusiness operators. Improved access to environmentally oriented credit enables farmers to invest in productive assets, expand cultivated land, and engage in value-added activities such as processing and storage, which directly contribute to poverty reduction.

Furthermore, the negative coefficient of climate change impacts on employment highlights how climate shocks deepen poverty by disrupting livelihoods. By contrast, green financing and the adoption of agricultural technology act as protective mechanisms, reducing vulnerability and income volatility. These findings underscore the role of inclusive green finance as a critical tool for building economic resilience among poor and climate-exposed households, in line with SDG 1.4, which emphasises equal access to economic resources and financial services.

SDG 2: Zero Hunger

SDG 2 focuses on ending hunger, achieving food security, improving nutrition, and promoting sustainable agriculture. The positive and significant effect of agricultural technology adoption on employment reflects broader productivity gains that are essential for food availability and stability. Climate-smart technologies such as improved seed varieties and irrigation systems enhance crop yields and reduce post-harvest losses, thereby strengthening local food systems in Northeast Nigeria.

By facilitating access to finance for climate-resilient agricultural investments, green financing supports sustainable intensification rather than environmentally destructive expansion. This aligns with SDGs 2.3 and 2.4, which aim to increase productivity and promote sustainable food production systems. The findings suggest that scaling up green finance and technology adoption can simultaneously address food insecurity and labour absorption, particularly in regions prone to recurrent climate stress.

SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth

SDG 8 emphasises promoting sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all. The regression results show that both green financing and agricultural technology significantly increase employment opportunities, validating agriculture's potential as a labour-absorbing sector even under climate stress.

Notably, the results indicate that employment gains extend beyond on-farm labour to agricultural value chains, including input supply, mechanisation services, processing, and marketing. This supports SDG 8.3, which calls for policies that promote productive activities, entrepreneurship, and job creation. By reducing investment risks and improving productivity, green financing fosters private sector participation and rural enterprise development, contributing to inclusive economic growth in Northeast Nigeria.

SDG 13: Climate Action

SDG 13 calls for urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts. The adverse, significant effect of climate change on employment confirms the urgency of climate adaptation interventions in agriculture. The study's findings demonstrate that green financing and climate-smart agricultural technologies are adequate adaptation and mitigation tools, reducing the adverse employment effects of climate variability. By enabling investments in water-efficient irrigation, drought-tolerant crops, and sustainable land management practices, green financing strengthens adaptive capacity and promotes low-carbon agricultural systems. This directly aligns with SDG 13.1 and SDG 13.3, which emphasise strengthening resilience and integrating climate change measures into national policies and planning. The evidence from Northeast Nigeria highlights the importance of embedding climate action within agricultural financing and employment strategies.

Integrated SDG Synergies

The study reveals strong synergies among SDGs 1, 2, 8, and 13, showing that climate action in agriculture can simultaneously reduce poverty, enhance food security, create decent jobs, and build resilience to climate change. The combined role of green financing and agricultural technology illustrates how integrated policy interventions can deliver multiple development outcomes, rather than isolated sectoral gains. This integrated approach is particularly critical for fragile and climate-exposed regions such as Northeast Nigeria.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study assessed the role of green financing and agricultural technology in mitigating the impacts of climate change and enhancing employment in Northeast Nigeria. Drawing on primary survey data and econometric analysis, the findings reveal that climate change significantly reduces agricultural employment, underscoring the vulnerability of agrarian livelihoods in the region. However, the results also demonstrate that access to green financing and the adoption of climate-smart agricultural technologies significantly and positively influence employment outcomes.

Specifically, green financing enables farmers and agribusinesses to invest in productive and climate-resilient inputs, expand agricultural operations, and engage in value-added activities that generate employment across agricultural value chains. Similarly, the adoption of agricultural technology enhances productivity, stabilises output under climate stress, and creates new employment opportunities in farming, processing, and related agribusiness services. The significance of extension services and education further highlights the importance of human capital in maximising the employment benefits of finance and technology.

Overall, the study provides empirical evidence that integrating green finance with climate-smart agricultural technologies offers a viable pathway to achieving climate resilience, generating employment, and fostering inclusive growth in Northeast Nigeria. The findings reinforce the interconnectedness of climate action, poverty reduction, food security, and decent work, in line with the Sustainable Development Goals.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

- i. **Scale up Green Financing Instruments:** Government and financial institutions should expand access to green loans, concessional credit, and climate finance tailored to smallholder farmers and agribusinesses in Northeast Nigeria. Risk-sharing mechanisms and interest rate subsidies can encourage private sector participation.
- ii. **Promote Climate-Smart Agricultural Technologies:** Public investment and targeted subsidies should support the widespread adoption of climate-resilient technologies such as improved seed varieties, efficient irrigation systems, mechanisation, and digital agricultural services.
- iii. **Strengthen Extension Services:** Integrating extension services with green finance programs will enhance farmers' capacity to effectively utilise financed technologies, thereby maximising productivity and employment outcomes.
- iv. **Enhance Financial Inclusion:** Policies aimed at reducing barriers to formal credit—particularly for women and youth—should be prioritised to ensure inclusive access to green financing opportunities.
- v. **Integrate Climate and Employment Policies:** Agricultural, climate, and employment policies should be harmonised to ensure that climate adaptation strategies explicitly incorporate job creation objectives, particularly within agricultural value chains.

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